

Acoustic Guitar

Treble Flute

Drumset

Drumset

Drumset

Hi-hat

Thundersheet

8

6

Guit.

Tr. Fl.

Drs.

Drs.

Drs.

Hi-hat

Thu.

8

10

Guit. 

Tr. Fl. 

Drs. 

Drs. 

Drs. 

Hi-hat 

Thu. 

13

Guit. 

Tr. Fl. 

Drs. 

Drs. 

Drs. 

Hi-hat 

Thu. 

16

Guit. 

Tr. Fl. 

Drs. 

Drs. 

Drs. 

Hi-hat 

Thu. 

19

Guit. 

Tr. Fl. 

Drs. 

Drs. 

Drs. 

Hi-hat 

Thu. 

23

Guit. 

Tr. Fl. 

Drs. 

Drs. 

Drs. 

Hi-hat 

Thu. 

29

Guit. 

Tr. Fl. 

Drs. 

Drs. 

Drs. 

Hi-hat 

Thu. 